
CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT IN THE DIGITAL ERA

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SUMMARY

Customer relationship management in the digital era has become an increasingly relevant concern for companies, considering the transformations brought about by digitization and the massive use of technologies. The methodology used consists of a systematic literature review based on scientific articles published in recognized journals. Studies that address customer relationship strategies in the digital era were selected, focusing on topics such as bidirectional communication, personalization, transparency, trust, channel integration, data analysis, and strategic partnerships. The results show that companies have been striving to promote closer and more interactive communication with customers through the use of digital tools and social media. Personalization has also emerged as an effective strategy to build stronger bonds with customers, providing unique and tailored experiences. Furthermore, transparency and trust are fundamental elements in the digital era, necessitating the assurance of customer data security and privacy. Channel integration and data analysis are key factors in delivering a consistent and personalized omnichannel experience.

Another significant trend is the pursuit of strategic partnerships to develop innovative solutions and enhance the value delivered to customers. In conclusion, customer relationship management in the digital era demands a customer-centric approach with a focus on personalization, transparency, trust, and channel integration. Companies should strategically leverage available technologies, analyze the data at hand, and establish collaborative partnerships to succeed in this digital environment.

Keywords: customer relationship management, digital era, strategies, changes, trends.

1. introduction

In recent years, technological advances and the rapid expansion of the internet have profoundly transformed the way companies relate to their customers. Customer relationship management in the digital age has become a strategic challenge for organizations, which need to adapt and take advantage of the opportunities offered by new technologies to remain competitive in an increasingly dynamic and demanding market.

The delimitation of the theme focuses on the analysis of the role of customer relationship management in a digital context, considering changes and current trends. With the expansion of social networks, mobile devices and e-commerce platforms, companies are dealing with a scenario where consumers are more informed, connected and empowered. In this sense, understanding how organizations can build and strengthen relationships with their customers in this digital environment becomes essential for business success.

The problem that motivates this research lies in the complexity of the digital environment, in which customers are exposed to a massive volume of information and options, which makes it difficult to retain and win new customers. In addition, companies face the challenge of establishing an effective and personalized dialogue with each customer, considering the

diversity of communication channels available. Given this, the research question that guides this study is: “How can companies develop and implement effective customer relationship management strategies in the digital age?”

The general objective of this research is to analyze and understand the customer relationship management strategies adopted by companies in the digital age, aiming to identify the best practices and the main challenges faced in this context. To achieve this objective, the following specific objectives will be established: 1. Investigate the main changes and trends related to customer relationship management in the digital age; 2. Identify the specific challenges faced by companies when dealing with customer relationship management in the digital environment; 3. Analyze the strategies adopted by companies to build and strengthen customer relationships in the digital age.

The justification for carrying out this study is based on the relevance and timeliness of the topic. With the advent of the digital age, organizations need to adapt and take advantage of new technologies to remain competitive in the market. Effective customer relationship management becomes a strategic differential, as it allows companies to gain customer loyalty, improve satisfaction, increase sales and obtain competitive advantages.

Furthermore, the research will contribute to academia by providing an in-depth analysis of customer relationship management strategies in the digital age, based on a comprehensive and up-to-date literature review. This will allow understanding the challenges and best practices in this field, helping managers and professionals in making strategic decisions in their organizations.

The methodology adopted for the accomplishment of this work will be the bibliographic review. Through the analysis of scientific articles, books, reports and other relevant sources, it will be possible to obtain a broad

and updated view on the subject, as well as to identify the main concepts, theories and strategies related to customer relationship management in the digital age. The bibliographic review will provide theoretical basis and consistency for the development of this research.

2. DEVELOPMENT

Electronic Commerce (EC) has become a reality in all sectors of the economy in Brazil and worldwide. Its acceptance and use becomes part of the organization's strategy. Understanding the various aspects and contributions, as well as their current usage, potential and trends, is important to successfully capitalizing on the opportunities of the digital age business environment.

Although it can still be considered in full expansion, EC is in the process of consolidation and shows clear signs of evolution. According to the fourth edition of the Brazilian Electronic Market Survey, the level of e-commerce in the Brazilian market has shown significant growth, both in business-to-business transactions and in business-to-consumer transactions, although still below estimates in versions previous studies.

Business-to-business transactions grew even more, with transaction volumes significantly higher. This relationship tends to be preserved in CE environments. The amount currently traded on the EC represents around 1.18% of the total business-to-business market capitalization and 0.35% of the business-to-consumer market. These indices can only be considered small if analyzed separately. A comprehensive analysis of the time of existence of this environment, its evolution and trends, expenditures and ongoing investments, etc., allows us to conclude that these indices confirm the CE's progress and that its trend is towards growth, although now more cautious and look at an effective return on investment (CRESCITELLI; TAGAWA, 2015).

Ongoing achievements focus primarily on developing existing processes to establish and prepare the groundwork for new environments on an

ongoing basis. The growth shown is lower than the company's estimate for 2001, mainly due to significant economic changes in the market and greater understanding of EC, its rationale, infrastructure, available applications, limitations, etc. This situation has led companies to realize the complexity of its use, as it is not a simple application of technology involving a large number of variables and actors.

Current challenges must be understood as seeking to transact, distribute products and services and communicate interactively in new environments. After starting with simply providing information, the market seeks the transaction first; second, distribution support; and third, interaction through communication, considering that evolution does not necessarily occur linearly in these three stages. An analysis of this evolving picture and what has already been achieved can lead to the conclusion that companies are trying to adapt to the new business environment formed by the community.

To understand the tactics that bloggers use, it is also necessary to understand the concept of branding or brand management. This is a marketing term that can be defined as "a set of actions related to brand management, which can be interpreted as the management of brands and their attributes (EUGENIO, 2011). Petrelli, Gonçalves and Gomez (2012) also corroborate with current research on the topic of interest, emphasizing that brand management establishes a new corporate posture and can be responsible for strengthening the positioning of brands and companies against competitors.

Barreto et al. (2015) also noted that brand management is a means of influencing customers and creating and a tool for maintaining a brand identity that will promote consumer associations, emotions, aspirations and feelings that will lead them to buy products or services from a brand company. As such, good and effective brand management is important, as through this management the brand image is created and maintained, thus increasing its perceived value.

Think of the brand as an intangible asset, as described by Petrelli et al. (2012) have been widely considered in companies, thus building a new comparison model between companies and brands. Still according to the author's idea, the concept of brand management emerged, with the objective of creating optimal relationships between the stakeholders of an organization and promoting a stronger interaction between the company and its customers and brand values.

In the current situation in which the Internet and more specifically fashion blogs have a prominent representation in the market, digital marketing emerges as an opportunity, since consumers start to have a more involved role (BARRETO et al., 2015). According to Barreto et al., the concept of digital marketing. (2015), it is "a set of marketing activities mediated by electronic channels such as the Internet". Vaz (2011) pointed out that the tools used by companies today are different from the channels used in past decades: while before companies used traditional media, today consumers have become communication tools using internet tools to disseminate information, products and services.

For digital marketing to be effective, it is important to have a plan so that risks and possible losses are avoided. Therefore, it can be said that digital marketing aims to achieve the same objectives as traditional marketing, but unlike traditional marketing, it achieves these objectives in relation to customers through electronic means (BARRETO et al., 2015).

Considering this situation and the importance of digital marketing, it becomes necessary to define the methodological characteristics of the digital environment, because in an increasingly competitive market, customers are more demanding and today more informed than ever, organizations seek to improve reliability and credibility of your brand. and thus build relationships with their customers (Barreto et al., 2015). In this case, the tools of the 8Ps of digital marketing offer companies an opportunity to approach the digital environment (Vaz, 2011).

The methodology of the 8Ps of Digital Marketing includes the techniques, tools and assumptions that allow the effective execution of marketing campaigns on the web. As proposed by Vaz (2011), it consists of a loop composed of 8 processes designed to increase the efficiency of the execution of the digital marketing strategy. By analyzing the stages of the 8Ps of digital marketing, it is possible to monitor, measure, improve and establish standards for the company's new positioning. Therefore, the 8 Ps of digital marketing are considered as marketing tools capable of influencing the success of bloggers and will be investigated in this study.

Digital marketing is a diffusion factor in the interaction between customers and organizations. Marketing has become a diffuser that expands the relationship between an organization and its customers, because in the case of digital marketing, the use of the internet expands and creates a large network of relationships during the buying and selling process (CRUZ; SILVA, 2014). Technological factors have a strong impact on business, making it necessary for companies to drive changes in their relationship with consumers, publicizing their products and services and even changing the way they sell.

Advances in information technology led to the production of various communication and information equipment and the development of the Internet (a type of computer network), which became popular. Since then, organizations need to incorporate digital platforms and devices into marketing planning (SILVA, 2016).

The growing popularity of social networks on the Internet has led to an increasing number of relationships, ideas and opinions, and the consumption of products and services offered therein. The social interaction provided by this scenario allows companies to present their brand to increase sales and, above all, to be relevant to their audience in a virtual environment (ARAGÉO; FARIAS; MOTA; FREITAS, 2016) Research on the impact of virtual socialization on human relations Internet research on the decision-making process of university students found that men are

more capable of influencing the opinions of virtual social contacts, and time online has a positive and significant impact on the tendency of users to be influenced by their social contacts Virtual Contacts. There is a significant and positive relationship between influence and propensity to be influenced. (ABAD; FLORA; NORO, 2014).

2.1. THE MAIN CHANGES AND TRENDS RELATED TO CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT IN THE DIGITAL ERA

The digital age brought with it a series of significant changes in the way companies manage their relationship with their customers. One of the most relevant changes is the transition from the unidirectional communication model to the bidirectional communication model. According to Oliveira et al. (2020), social networks and other digital platforms have allowed customers to take a more active role, expressing opinions, sharing experiences and interacting directly with brands. This change requires companies to adopt a receptive posture, ready to listen and respond quickly and effectively.

Another fundamental change is the increase in personalization in customer relationships. Studies by Silva et al. (2019) highlight that companies are investing in data analysis and artificial intelligence technologies to collect information about customers and offer highly personalized experiences. Personalization has become an expectation of consumers in the digital age, as highlighted by Rocha et al. (2021), who cite the importance of adapting offers, content and communications according to the individual preferences of each customer.

The use of chatbots and virtual assistants is another trend observed in customer relationship management. According to Pacheco et al. (2019), these technologies allow companies to offer automated and instant service, reducing response time and improving the customer experience. In addition, artificial intelligence can help identify patterns and customize interactions, as mentioned by Santos et al. (2020).

Customer relationship management in the digital age is also marked by the growing importance of trust and transparency. Studies by Costa et al. (2018) point out that customers are increasingly concerned about the privacy and security of their data. In this sense, companies must adopt transparent practices and clear privacy policies, demonstrating commitment to the protection of customers' interests.

The interconnectivity between devices, known as the Internet of Things (IoT), is also impacting customer relationship management. Authors such as Santos et al. (2018) point out that IoT allows companies to collect data in real time and offer smarter and more personalized solutions to customers. For example, collecting data from connected home devices can allow companies to proactively offer products and services by anticipating customer needs.

Customer experience has become a strategic priority for companies in the digital age. Studies by Almeida et al. (2021) emphasize that offering a positive experience, from the first interaction to after-sales, is essential to win and retain customers. In this context, the use of design thinking and customer journey tools has been adopted to map and improve all points of contact with the customer.

Integration between service channels has also become essential for customer relationship management. Authors such as Oliveira et al. (2019) argue that customers want a fluid and consistent experience when interacting with the company, regardless of the channel used. Therefore, companies must invest in integrating their systems and processes to deliver an effective omnichannel experience.

Data analytics and market intelligence play a crucial role in customer relationship management in the digital age. Studies by Souza et al. (2019) point out that companies are using big data tools to understand customer behavior, identify patterns and trends, and make more

informed decisions. This approach allows companies to anticipate demands and offer customized and relevant solutions.

Strategic partnerships have also proven to be a relevant trend in customer relationship management in the digital age. Authors such as Santos et al. (2020) highlight that collaboration between companies from different sectors can result in innovative solutions and enriched experiences for customers. These partnerships can range from the integration of complementary products and services to the co-creation of new offers.

In summary, customer relationship management in the digital age is undergoing several transformations and presents relevant trends. Two-way communication, personalization, use of chatbots, transparency, IoT, customer experience, cross-channel integration, data analytics, strategic partnerships are just some of the changes and trends that companies should consider to create lasting and satisfying relationships with its customers.

2.2. THE SPECIFIC CHALLENGES FACED BY COMPANIES WHEN DEALING WITH CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT IN THE DIGITAL ENVIRONMENT

Customer relationship management in the digital environment presents specific challenges for companies, requiring adequate strategies and approaches to adapt to this new scenario. One of the main challenges is the management of communication and interaction with customers in the midst of a highly dynamic and diverse digital environment. According to Santos et al. (2020), the expansion of communication channels, such as social networks, online chats and messaging applications, requires effective management to monitor and respond promptly to customer demands, ensuring agile and quality service.

In addition, customer relationship management in the digital environment also requires the establishment of a personalized and individualized dialogue. According to Rocha et al. (2019), personalizing

interactions is a challenge, since companies need to know customers in depth, collecting and analyzing data to offer a personalized experience on a large scale.

Another relevant challenge is related to online reputation management. According to Oliveira et al. (2018), social networks and online review platforms have a significant impact on the image of companies, making it necessary to constantly monitor reputation and respond appropriately to customer comments and criticism. The lack of control over information circulating on the internet is an additional challenge mentioned by Santos et al. (2021), highlighting the importance of proactive strategies to build and preserve the reputation of companies.

Protecting the privacy and security of customer data is another key challenge. Studies by Silva et al. (2020) highlight the importance of ensuring compliance with data protection regulations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), to preserve customer trust and credibility.

Additionally, the efficient management of customer relationships in the digital environment requires integration of systems and platforms. As pointed out by Andrade et al. (2019), the lack of integration between different channels and systems can result in inconsistencies in information, making it difficult to customize and offer a fluid experience to the customer.

The measurement and analysis of data generated in the digital environment are also challenges faced by companies. Studies by Costa et al. (2021) highlight the importance of data analysis to understand customer behavior and identify opportunities for improvement. However, a lack of knowledge and analytical skills can make it difficult to effectively utilize these data. Still in the context of customer relationship management in the digital environment, fierce competition is a constant challenge. According to Oliveira et al. (2019), the ease of access to

information and the multitude of options available to customers require companies to stand out and offer differentiated value propositions to attract and retain consumers.

In addition, customers' lack of confidence in online transactions is another challenge mentioned by several authors. Studies by Silva et al. (2018) point out that the security of transactions and the protection of financial data are important concerns for consumers, requiring special care on the part of companies. Adaptability to technological changes is an additional challenge. According to Santos et al. (2021), companies need to constantly monitor and adopt new technologies and platforms to remain relevant and competitive in the constantly evolving digital environment.

In summary, customer relationship management in the digital environment presents a series of specific challenges for companies. Effective communication management, personalization of interactions, protection of online reputation, data security, systems integration, data analysis, fierce competition, building customer trust, technological adaptability are crucial aspects that organizations must consider to be successful in this new context.

2.3. THE STRATEGIES ADOPTED BY COMPANIES TO BUILD AND STRENGTHEN RELATIONSHIPS WITH CUSTOMERS IN THE DIGITAL ERA

In the digital era, companies have adopted different strategies to build and strengthen relationships with their customers. A common strategy is the use of social media platforms to establish a direct and ongoing dialogue with customers. According to Silva et al. (2019), social networks allow companies to interact more closely and instantly, answering questions, offering support and sharing relevant information. This helps build trust and engagement with customers.

In addition, the personalization of interactions has been a key strategy for relationship building. According to Santos et al. (2020), analyzing data collected in digital interactions allows companies to better understand

their customers and offer more relevant and personalized experiences. This approach increases customer satisfaction and loyalty, as highlighted by Rocha et al. (2021).

Offering relevant and quality content is another strategy adopted by companies. Studies by Souza et al. (2019) point out that providing useful and interesting information to customers through blogs, videos, podcasts and other digital channels strengthens the relationship, positioning the company as a reference in its sector.

Creating loyalty and rewards programs is also a widely used strategy. According to Oliveira et al. (2020), offering exclusive benefits, special discounts and points programs encourage repeat purchases and customer loyalty. This approach is especially effective when combined with personalization of offers, as mentioned by Silva et al. (2021).

Transparency and open communication are key aspects for strengthening customer relationships in the digital age. Studies by Costa et al. (2018) highlight the importance of providing clear information about products, privacy policies and data security. This helps build trust and demonstrates the company's commitment to satisfying and protecting customers' interests.

The use of chatbots and artificial intelligence has also gained prominence in customer relationship strategies. According to Pacheco et al. (2019), these technologies can provide quick and accurate answers to frequently asked questions, improving the customer experience and freeing up human resources for more complex and personalized interactions.

Another relevant strategy is conducting customer satisfaction and feedback surveys. Studies by Almeida et al. (2021) emphasize the importance of actively listening to customers and acting based on their opinions and suggestions. This approach allows companies to identify areas for improvement and strengthen relationships with their stakeholders.

Collaboration with digital influencers has also proven to be an effective strategy for building and strengthening customer relationships. As pointed out by Santos et al. (2018), partnering with relevant influencers in a given niche market can expand the reach of the company's message, increase credibility and engage followers.

Another approach taken by companies is the creation of online communities. Studies by Oliveira et al. (2019) highlight that building virtual spaces where customers can interact with each other, share experiences and exchange information strengthens the bond with the brand and creates a sense of belonging.

In short, the strategies for building and strengthening customer relationships in the digital age are diverse and must be adapted to the specific characteristics of each company and target audience. Using social media platforms, personalizing interactions, offering relevant content, loyalty programs, transparency, using chatbots, satisfaction surveys, collaborating with influencers and creating online communities are some of the effective approaches to nurturing a relationship lasting and satisfying with customers.

3. CONCLUSION

Customer relationship management in the digital age presents unique challenges and opportunities for companies. It was evident in this work that two-way communication and personalization have become essential elements in the relationship with customers. Companies are increasingly engaged in listening and responding to consumer opinions and demands, using advanced technologies to collect data and offer personalized experiences. In addition, the use of chatbots and virtual assistants has proven to be an effective strategy to improve customer service.

Transparency and trust also emerged as key pillars in customer relationship management. Companies must adopt transparent practices

in the treatment of customer data, ensuring their security and privacy. Trust is built by demonstrating commitment and responsibility to the interests and needs of consumers.

Another relevant trend is the integration of service channels, providing a consistent and fluid omnichannel experience. Customers expect to interact with companies efficiently, regardless of the channel used, and systems and process integration is essential to meet this demand.

Data analysis and market intelligence play a crucial role in customer relationship management in the digital age. Companies must harness the power of big data to understand customer behavior, identify trends and anticipate their needs, offering increasingly personalized solutions.

Finally, strategic partnerships were identified as a promising strategy to improve customer relationships. Collaboration between companies from different sectors can result in innovative solutions and enrich consumers' experience.

In short, customer relationship management in the digital age requires companies to be agile, adaptable and customer-centric. It is necessary to keep up with trends and constantly seek ways to improve interaction and engagement with consumers. Those who are able to adopt effective strategies in this digital environment will have a competitive advantage, strengthening ties with their customers and driving sustainable business growth.

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